

Economic Prosperity and Education are Two Sides of the Same Coin: Role Analysis of Public and Private Educational Sectors for Economic Growth

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 07 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 11 , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Education, Economic Prosperity, Socio-Economic Growth, Public And Private Educational Blocks</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5562768</p>	<p><i>While education broadens one's horizons, it also assists people in keeping up with the current world's pace. This goal can only be fulfilled by professionals and experts with the necessary experience and knowledge, such as economists, scientists, engineers, technicians, educators, and managers. These professionals assist in the effective and efficient formulation, facilitation, and implementation of economic development growth policies. The study looks into the two types of education in Pakistan: private and public, and suggests ways to improve both while focusing on economic prosperity. Pakistan's literacy rate is rather poor. The government needs to make significant efforts to promote literacy rate rapidly. At present it is 58 percent, which is far below than numerous other nations of the world. This paper assesses and suggests plan to promote state education by overcoming weaknesses and challenges through the induction of highly trained instructors, a technologically and scientifically educated workforce, and the much-needed intellectual resources. The absence of resources, according to this report, limits scientific and technological education. Pakistan spends on education approximately 2.5 percent of GDP, which is inadequate when compared to the size of the people that needs to be educated. This study was based on a quantitative survey, interviews and questionnaires conducted in District South. A quality education framework helps a country achieve the desired socioeconomic enhancement by helping residents to keep up with the evolving requirements of the dynamic world.</i></p>

Introduction

A country's socioeconomic success is largely dependent on its educational system. It also boosts productivity, job creation, and general economic growth. Education is the most important pillar for progress, as it is the corner stone upon which our social wellbeing is constructed. It improves the workforce's interpersonal reliability and financial sustainability, hence developing human resource, which leads to poverty alleviation and a better lifestyle (Rasool, 2007). Across the globe there are two primary types of education systems: private and public. In order to assure the nation's progressive and continuous growth, private educational institutions have gone mainstream. Education has a key role in the growth every nation in the dynamic era (Awan, A. G., & Zia, A., 2015). He highlights the importance of international rivalry in technology and education in a country's progress. He goes on to say that Pakistan has a variety of educational institutions, but they are primarily separated into state schools.

Only education, which aids in the structuring of human competencies and the acceleration of economic growth through knowledge and skills through creativity, can help a nation to attain socioeconomic development. Education's progressive outcomes can aid in poverty reduction, health facilitation, and inequality reduction. Good governance is also beneficial in the implementation of socioeconomic programmes. The various characteristics of education are the most significant aspects in forming a national strategy. It is essential for emerging economies to restructure their educational systems with the goal of increasing productivity in many industries by hiring skilled workers and pursuing development for quick growth. (Glewwe, 2002) Unsustainable economic growth has been a problem for Pakistan for decades. Political instability, economic expansion, and a lack of interest from international investors were the main causes of these situations. High inflation leads to unstable economic growth, which has negative consequences for the budget deficit, debt servicing, rising foreign debt, international market for Pakistani goods, and a scarcity of human and physical capital. Furthermore, political turmoil, global warming, and an absence of law and order all contribute to economic instability. A country's education sector can not thrive without economic stability. As a result, education requires special attention in order to achieve state economic progress. In developing countries, education benefits people by providing them with good decision-making power and instilling gender equality. Education assists people in making better decisions and raising their living standards (Aslam et al., 2017). The focus of this research is on Pakistan's school educational system and its role in fostering economic growth

and development. It is critical for the country's education and human capability to flourish.

In order to improve the economy's growth performance, the authorities have to enhance funding, particularly for public school education. Furthermore, this research primarily focuses on the preschool to secondary education system in Karachi's District South, and compares and offers strategies to enhance and overcome flaws in our educational framework.

Literature Review:

Education has a significant impact on society because it aids in economic sustainability along with carrying about certain reforms that lead to innovation and societal improvement. Compared to private education, public education is less expensive and more accessible. Furthermore, it establishes a democratic educational system (Maqsoodah, 1998).

Pakistan is a progressing state that was established on August 14, 1947. In the past, the country encountered numerous hurdles in its efforts to improve its economy and education, and every ruling body continues to face new challenges. According to Article 37-B of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan's 1973 Constitution, the government is responsible for ensuring free and obligatory education up to the secondary level within a certain time frame (Parveen A. et al., 2011). There are two types of educational systems in Pakistan: private and public. Both regimes include five years of primary schooling, three years of secondary, two years of high school (Matric/GCSE), and two years of higher secondary education (FA/FSc. Level/A' Level). Despite their similar educational architecture, the main differences between these two systems are in terms of policies and funding. The public education system is heavily reliant on state funds; yet, the system has decentralized and regions have made responsible for general educational management (Aslam, 2017). Because of their low literacy rates, the majority of developing countries face socio-political and economic difficulties such as inflation, poor earnings, corruption, rising population, and civil unrest. Education raises awareness and helps to control societal ills to a large extent. Since the globe has become a global community, it has become increasingly important for residents to keep up with the rapid pace of change, which can only be accomplished by means of adequate education and knowledge.

Education improves knowledge and abilities necessary for dealing with difficult circumstances and creating effective solutions. (Kazmi, S. W., & Quran, H. 2005). Any country, developed or developing, can make economic progress. For its success and progress, Pakistan emphasises education and the development of a skilled and productive workforce. Education is a critical factor in determining a country's economic growth by increasing human capital and narrowing the gap between rich and poor or middle-class people's wages. (Bils, M., & Klenow, P. J. 2000)

Higher education plays an important part in the country's economic development. Consequently, there is more skilled labour available, which has a beneficial impact on GDP. Higher education, on the other hand, is costly, and it is influenced by three factors: education, cost, enrollment, and the availability of a skilled labour force, as well as GDP. N. U. R. Khattak, N. U. R. Khattak, N. U. R. Khattak, N. No country can hope to achieve economic progress without professionals such as scientists, economists, technicians, engineers, and mid-level managers. Education is the only way to reach this goal. (Depersio, G. 2018). In the opinion of (Klasen & Lamanna, 2009), the more educated citizens are, the better their output will be since higher education will broaden their perspectives, allowing them to come up with new ideas and procedures. As a result of the increased production, there is a new motivation to encourage a society to pursue higher education (Cooray, A. V. 2009). Pakistan has faced numerous challenges in reaching its educational objectives. Regulations and doctrinal planning were some of the controlling constraints. Language diversity, political turmoil, demographic pressure, socioeconomic progress, and improvement are all controlling factors. As a result,

Pakistan must examine its policies and take steps to address extra demands and expectations. The tendency toward developing even more private educational institutions is growing as a result of a lack of funds in the public sector of education. Consequently, there has been a significant drop in educational quality. (Ghazi et al., 2010). The government funds education and allocates resources to the public sector based on the needs and objectives of the country. These investments have proven to be effective in reaching educational goals and producing skilled workers (Mupimpila, C., & Narayana, N., 2009).

The government covers all of the costs associated with public schools, including teacher salaries, land and construction costs, and maintenance. Public schools have a responsibility to maximize the government's investment by teaching as many students as feasible. Since public schools are supervised by the government, they can charge relatively minimal fees and supply course books for free up to matriculation. The government requires specialists and qualified workers, and as a result, it spends a significant amount of money on education in order to produce people who will be able to service the economy in the future. While controlling school curricula, the government also keeps a close watch on the form and nature of work force that will be created by the education industry in keeping the economy balanced, as a surplus will raise unemployment if supply exceeds demand. This supply and demand issue may lead to government interference in the educational system. Considering Pakistan has an ideolog

ical foundation, the government must monitor the type and quality of education delivered in schools to guarantee that the essential ideological concepts are not jeopardized.. (Khaliq, F., & Ahmed, W. 2018).

Education leads to increased productivity and economic growth in addition to increasing human capital. On the otherhand, a low educational rate leads to low productivity and low economic growth. As a result, investing in education reaps dividends in the form of trained labour, which boosts effectiveness and improve a country's economic standing. It is critical to focus resources on education that develops technical skills such as technicians, scientists, administrators, managers, and engineers, all of which contribute to the building of human capital.

There will be excessive unemployment and brain drain unless a robust manpower formation is built, which is not uncommon in Pakistan. Pakistan's growth rate is 2.1 percent, whereas unemployment is 5.6 percent and underemployment is 16 percent, indicating a lack of educational planning and operational directional mistake. People are unaware of health issues or nutrition as a result of weak or absent educational planning and administration, and their lifestyles are not as healthy as they should be in industrialized nations. Student teacher ratio is a vital element in the educational process. Other considerations include resource allocation, management capabilities, and quality control.

Quality assurance is the process of ensuring that educational resources and knowledge are used effectively in order to achieve the desired objectives. Internal and external inspection, monitoring, and well defined quality system standards could be used to achieve it (Omoniyi, M. B. I. 2013). In Pakistan, technical and vocational education has received little emphasis. In our country, there are insufficient numbers of such institutes, as well as a shortage of infrastructure, qualified and skilled teachers, and sufficient resources. When a country's entire population becomes trained, it can become one of its most valuable assets. If there are more unemployed and unskilled people, this can have a detrimental impact on national development. As a result, technical education must be prioritized by the government (Jabarullah & Hussain, 2019). With each day technology advances rapidly increasing, and the previous mode and style of work get obsolete. As a result, keeping up with ever - changing trends and innovations is critical, as is taking proper efforts to not just accomplish through outstanding education, but also to create and efficiently utilise a strong workforce in order to enhance productivity and contribute to a country's economic success (World Economic Forum, 2016). It is necessary for the workers to be perfect in academic, technology, and mathematical skills, as well as the ability to perform critical analysis, collaborate, and communicate with a variety of situations and individuals. To achieve this, individuals should be committed to their task and do it with integrity, as these are necessary ingredients for a good outcome (Bailey, 1995).

Technology has a substantial influence on today's classrooms: it changes the entire structure of the environment as well as the processes of educational activities. The level of education a person has has a varying effect on earnings; the more skillful an employee is, the greater his income earnings, and thus the more advantageous to any country's socioeconomic conditions (Psacharopoulos, 1994). According to study, even a 1% secondary level educated labour force has a 40 to 60% favourable influence on the less educated bottom class (Bourguignon, F., Goh, C. C., & Kim, D. I. 2004).

The conceptual framework is represented in figure 1

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework:

Objectives of the study

- To determine the causes and shortcomings of the educational system's failure to achieve desired economic-growth-and-development.
- To investigate the function of education in poverty alleviation through socioeconomic advancement in education.

Research Hypotheses

1. There is a significant variation in perspective between the private and public education sectors. In terms of standard of living and contribution to economic development and growth.

2. There is a relationship between education and poverty reduction strategies.
3. It is necessary to develop an effective and corruption-free education system that is compatible, acknowledged, and accepted by other advanced countries throughout the world.

Research Design

The cross-sectional survey research approach is used extensively in this comparison study. It is a research strategy based on a comprehensive literature and semi-structured discussions with concerned authorities, in which a closed-ended questionnaire is constructed based on the role of education in encouraging economic-growth-and-development. The study's population consisted of the overall community who were involved in the school education sector. A specific aim-oriented baseline survey was done to determine the true cause for education's role to economic-growth-and-development. This survey used to have a number of respondents of 300 people, and the gathered information was presented in a tabular format. The reliability and validity test yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70, indicating that our scale has a high level of internal consistency in both private and public samples.

Table 1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.730	15

The reliability of the research instrument is found to be above 0.730, hence, the research results can be assumed as reliable and valid.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Interviews with the Director General and the Registrar of the Director Inspection/Registration of Private Institutions, Sindh Karachi, yielded qualitative data. The open-ended research questions provided the basis for the primary analysis. According to private education experts, the government should raise education spending to determine the elements impacting economic growth and progress in the educational system; higher education spending may have a good effect on economic growth. A larger investment in education can assist Pakistan's economy become more productive. It is critical to developing an appropriate educational system, with legislation and structure in place to prepare for the promotion of education in the country. After the 18th amendment, education became a government topic. As a result, governments must develop educational policies and regulations to ensure that students receive a high-quality education. Increased investment in human capital results in a higher-quality workforce. This would eventually lead to improved skills, abilities, and training. Because skilled workers are more productive, the skilled labour force has a considerable impact on growth. Because the number of technical and vocational institutes is insufficient, many are lacking in infrastructure, teachers, and training instruments. One of the most important components of a country's national might is its people. Once it is skilled, it becomes an advantage; yet, an unskilled population means more jobless people in the country, negatively impacting national progress.

In-service teacher training for newly hired teachers should be provided to increase the efficiency and quality of education in Sindh. Academic assistance for teachers should be provided through district and regional resource centres, along with "special teaching" for learner development of Information technology activities in schools and basic technical courses, which should also be considered necessary at the secondary education. A revised curriculum/syllabus should also be used to build an educational institution monitoring system. According to experts from both the private and public sectors, the public education system is declining due to high dropout rates at the primary level, low budget allocation, different standards of education, low quality teaching standards and textbooks, political interference, increased population, and unemployment.

According to the two people who were interviewed, education plays a critical role in reducing poverty by improving socioeconomic conditions in education. Furthermore, education is a focused activity with significant

implications for both individuals and nations. It primarily aids in job creation, poverty alleviation, and increasing export rates. Education aids in the reduction of poverty, the acceleration of economic growth, and the increase of income. It also improves a person's chances of living a healthy life and lowers death rates. To summarise, education is one of the most important investments a country can make in its people and future.

The following tasks should be undertaken, according to the Directorate General of Education and an educationalist from the government sector, to put the current educational system in accordance with the modern system.: Teachers should be motivated by competitive compensation incentives, in-service training, and greater competency awards; excess should be directed to high-quality early childhood education programmes; and the recruitment process should be prioritised. Secondary school technical education should be required. The experts also proposed numerous educational improvements, such as offering financial incentives to students, which would result in a lower drop-out rate. The government should take adequate measures to eradicate corruption from the educational system, as it is one of the factors contributing to Pakistan's overall low literacy rate. As a result, both private and public education departments require an effective monitoring system for this reason. The government should prioritise technical education, and more financing should be allocated to education that contributes to beneficial economic growth.

Quantitative Data Analysis

Table 2: The educational system contributes to the country's economic-growth-and-development.

		SD	D	N	A	SA	Total
INSTITUTE	public	1	29	11	103	6	150
	private	6	14	31	84	15	150
Total		7	43	42	187	21	300

According to the descriptive statistics of the preceding statement, the majority of respondents in both the public and private sectors believe that our educational system contributes to the country's economic-growth-and-development.

Table 3: Education has improved the living standards of the public.

		D	N	A	SA	Total
INSTITUTE	Public	27	15	96	12	150
	Private	9	9	84	48	150
Total		36	24	180	60	300

When the findings are compared, Table 3 reveals that the majority of private and public sector participants agreed, but the majority of private sector respondents strongly believe that "education has enhanced the people's living standard." As a consequence of the survey findings, it can be stated that there is no difference in view between respondents from the private and public sectors of education when it comes to education's contribution to higher living standards.

Table 4: As the literacy rate rises, more career prospects open up in other countries.

		SD	D	N	A	SA	Total
INSTITUTE	Public	47	56	11	31	3	150
	Private	1	23	15	81	30	150
Total		48	79	26	112	22	300

When the data are compared, it is clear that the public sector disagrees, however the private sector agrees that "an increase in literacy rate does bring greater work prospects abroad." As a result, the report's findings reveal that respondents have conflicting feelings about the breadth of local education in other countries. It was highlighted during the poll that this, too, is related to economic factors, as well as the quality of education and skill, rather than a simple choice.

Hypothesis 1 : There is a significant variation in perspective between the private and public education sectors. In terms of standard of living and contribution to economic development and growth.

Table 5

PearsonCorrelations			
		Hyp1	Dependent
Hypothesis.1	Pearson Correlation.	1.0	.246**
	.Sig_ (2-tailed.)		.000_
	.N.	300	300_
Dependent.	Pearson_Correlation..	.246**	1_
	.Sig. (2-tailed).	.000	
	.N.	300.	300_

**Correlation_is_significant_at the. 0.01_level_(2-tailed.).

Table: 6

Correlations.			
		Hyp1	Dependent
.Spearm.an's rho.	Hyp.1	.Correlation..Coefficient	1.000.
		..Sig. (2-tailed) ..	.000
		..N.	300.
.Dependent..	.Dependent..	.Correlation Coefficient..	.263.**
		Sig. (2-tailed.).	.000.
		N..	300.

**Correlation_is_significant_at the. 0.01_level_(2-tailed.).

The correlational_ test techniques were used, and the value of p was found to be less than 0.05, indicating that the first-hypothesis is supported. Given that the correlation coefficient between the manipulated and reacted variables is less than 30%, it is reasonable to assume that the combined views of public-and-private-sectors education have minimal effect on Pakistan's economic success.

Hypothesis 2 . There is a relationship between education and poverty reduction strategies.

Table: 7

Correlations_			
		Hyp_2	Dependent_
Hyp_2	Pearson_Correlation.	-1_	_0.371**
	Sig_(2-tailed).		.000
	N_	-300	300
Dependent	Pearson_Correlation.	-0.371**	1
	Sig_(2-tailed).	.000	
	N.	300	300

**Correlation_is_significant_at the. 0.01_level_(2-tailed.).

Table: 8

Correlations			
		Hyp2	Dependent
-Spearman's rho	Hyp2	Correlation Coefficient.	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed).	.000

	N.	300	300
Dependent	Correlation Coefficient.	.483**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed).	.000	.
	N.	300	300

** . Correlation_is_ significant_at the. 0.01_level_(2-tailed.).

The Pearson-and-Spearman test results were analysed, and the p value was found to be less-than-0.05, indicating that the second hypothesis is accepted. - However, because both tests' correlation coefficients are approximately 50%, the results show that the two variables have a moderate association, and it can be inferred that education can moderately alleviate poverty in the country.

Hypothesis 3. It is necessary to develop an effective and corruption-free education system that is compatible, acknowledged, and accepted by other advanced countries throughout the world.

Table 9

Correlations			
		Hyps3	Dependent
Hyp 4	Pearson. Correlation..	1.	0.391.**
	Sig. (2-tailed). .		.000
	N.	300	300
Dependent.	Pearson Correlation.	.391**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed).	.000	
	N.	300	300

** .Correlation_is_ significant_at the. 0.01_level_(2-tailed.).

Table 10.

Correlations.				
			Hyp_3	Dependent_.
Spearman's rho	Hyp_3	Correlation_Coefficient.	1.000.	.409.**
		Sig_(2-tailed).	.	.000
		N.	300	300
	Dependent	Correlation Coefficient.	.409**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed).	.000	.
		N.	300	300

** . Correlation_is_ significant_at the. 0.01_level_(2-tailed.).

The Pearson and Spearman tests were used, and it was discovered that the research obtained a p value-less-than 0.05, indicating that the third research hypothesis, that the association between the-two-variables is moderate, is accepted because the correlation coefficient of both-tests is nearly 40%. Pakistan's economic growth is moderately influenced by an effective and corruption-free education system.

Conclusion and Discussion

This study was targeted to relate the private-and-public. sectors. of school learning and their role of supporting economic growth and improvement in the country. This relative study was mostly based on computableinvestigationenquiry method which is also reflected as the correlational method research design.The study's sample included 300 educators from both private and public schools in Karachi's west area. 150 respondents worked in the private education sector, while the remaining 150 worked in the public education sector. A well designsurvey research instrument was organized in view and the responses for each of the statement were recorded by using a five-point Likert Scale. The reliability test resulted in a value of almost 0.7, indicating a high level of internal consistency.Descriptive and Inferential statistics was conducted with significance noted at $p < 0.05$ were used for hypotheses testing. The appropriate literature was studiedand cited from many differentresources.The importance of education in encouraging economic-growth-and-development in the country was stressed in this study.Education improves people's living standards, a higher literacy rate leads to better job opportunities abroad, a concrete educational policy, including funding for public education, is beneficial to economic development, and there is a need to combat corruption and malpractice in the educational sector, according to the study's findings. Furthermore, economic expansion necessitates technical education in addition to theoretical education at universities. Last but not least, education has just a little impact on health awareness, which has to be reconsidered and further research or improvement.

The hypothesis testing results, on the other hand, suggest that we agree the facts that there is a major difference in opinions about living standards and contributions to economic-growth-and-development between the private and public sectors of education. It is also largely assumed that education aids in the attainment of higher employment chances and that students become more attentive and cooperative as a result of their education. According to the current findings, only effective education can help to reduce poverty; Students may get degrees, but they may not have a successful profession due to a lack of proper skills and learning, and they may be ineligible for government support if corruption and inefficiency prevail in the educational sector.

The current study compares both public and private secondary educational institutes and their impact on socio-economic prosperity and growth of Pakistan. The theme of the study analyses its contribution to relevant factors, which affect the living standards of the stakeholders. It elaborates both the educational pillars in the country and its related factors, while investigating the prevailing issues encountered by the both systems, which helped in developing comparative study. It also suggests remedies for the uplifting of educational standards in Pakistani schooling systems. This study shades light on the need of economic growth through educational reform and the prosperity of Pakistani society as it has multiple shades on living standards, eradication poverty, health awareness, employability, skills development, women empowerment, better infrastructure and so on so forth. All these factors facilitate on the enhancement of human capital. One cannot deny the proportional relation between economic growth and a solid educational foundation from the primary to secondary cadre. The said study also highlights people's preferences for choosing one sector of education over the other for various reasons. The lower income class in Pakistan generally approach public schools, which are subject to bad management, poor infrastructure and low quality of education as contrast to private sector of institutions which are approached by economically sound slot of the society. The people catered here and comparatively better educated, skilled and technically sound. These lot contribute in the economic growth of the nation but their numbers are thin. It is also noted that usually students belonging to lower income families get admitted to public schools due to factors quite opposite related to the upper middle class.

Nearly every single aspect of public and private schools has been thoroughly examined in this study, confirming the conclusion that "education is a foundation to growth and development." The only way to attain significant development and growth is through the human intellect. Quality education in both public and private sector of schools can yield quality health care facilities, innovation in public administration and the nation can be benefitted through its human capital at its best.

Education is a key component of economic growthdevelopment, if the economy grows well, people's quality of life improves, and they are able to enjoy the benefits of freedom of thought and expression, allowing them to join a strong socio-economic culture of the world.

Compared to private education, public education is less expensive and more accessible. Furthermore, it establishes a democratic learning environment(Maqsoodah, 1998). Because of their low literacy rates, the majority of developing countries face socio-political and economic difficulties such as inflation, inadequate wages, corruption, rising population, and political turmoil. Education raises awareness and helps to control societal ills to a large extent. Since the planet has become a global community, it is increasingly important for residents to adapt to the rapid pace of change, which can only be accomplished via adequate education and knowledge. Education improves proficiency and abilities, which are necessary for dealing with difficult circumstances and creating workable responses (Kazmi, 2004). The aforesaid research is comparative study established on phenomenological and quantitative survey pattern. Two of the study instruments are two separate interviews with educational specialists, and the analyst also employed a closed-ended questionnaire focused on the impact of education in encouraging socio-economic development. Due to the large scope of the investigation and time constraints, the study is confined to District South using convenience sample methods. The researcher utilized SPSS for statistical analysis to test each hypothesis. The main findings of the study show that there is a significant difference in opinion between the private and public regimes of education in terms of standard of living and contribution to economic development. It is also accepted that education also aids in obtaining maximum employment options, and that people get more and more alert and aware of their own selves and surroundings. The current study demonstrates that only quality education can assist in reducing poverty; nevertheless, if corruption and incompetence prevail in the education industry, pupils could earn degrees but may not have a promising career due to the absence of appropriate skills and understanding.

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